

PATIENT ATTITUDES TO PAID SPECIALIST VISITS**Stoyanova Ts.***Doctoral candidate in the Department of Health Economics, Faculty of Public Health „Prof. Tzekomir Vodenicharov, MD, DSc”, Medical University – Sofia***ABSTRACT**

The patients' access to medical care is a fundamental component of public health system assessment. After the establishment of the general practitioner institution, the access to specialist outpatient care is conducted after a specialist referral is secured. The National Health Insurance Fund operates on a fixed budget that's established by law, and there is no funding for payments in case physicians report more physical exams. In case the limit for referrals is reached, any health-insured person may be declined the opportunity for a physical exam and the needed medical care may not be covered by the budget, to which the patient contributes on a regular basis. Patients constantly complain about the insufficient number of referrals. In this regard we conducted a questionnaire-based survey among patients to find their attitudes to paid physical exams by specialist physicians. The results show that 61.3% of the participants do not fully approve of paid specialist physical exams. The main advantages of paid exams that the respondents point to are that those exams are carried out with better tools and in better conditions (39.7 %) and that they are conducted more promptly (39.5 %). 68.4 % of the participants are willing to fully cover the cost of a physical exam with a specialist in case of emergency or urgency, while 51.1 % in case they need to get a second opinion for an existing diagnosis.

Keywords: specialist, paid exam, advantages, price.

Introduction:

The patients' access to medical care is a fundamental component of public health system assessment. Access is a complex multi factor term for which there is no unified universal definition. Generally, access to health services is understood as the timely provision of medical care to the people who need it, without any serious restrictions, consistent with their individual needs and independently from their financial capabilities. According to Bulgarian legislation, it is the right of every Bulgaria citizen to receive medical help, under the terms and procedure established in the Health Act and Health Insurance Act.

The terms and procedure for realising the right to access medical care are determined with an ordinance by the Council of Ministers. Health-insured persons in the Republic of Bulgaria have the right to receive medical help in the scope of the basic health services package guaranteed by the budget of the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF). This package provides access to affordable treatments according to the stage, development, severity and acuteness of the respective condition.

After the establishment of the general practitioner institution, the access to specialist outpatient care is conducted after a specialist referral is secured. NHIF covers payments for care delivered by a specialised medical care provider to a health-insured person who was given a referral by a primary and/or specialised outpatient care (SOC) provider, who has entered into a contract with NHIF.

The National Health Insurance Fund operates on a fixed budget that's established by law, and there is no funding for payments in case physicians report more physical exams. In case the limit for referrals is reached, any health-insured person may be declined the opportunity for a physical exam and the needed medical care may not be covered by the budget, to which the patient contributes on a regular basis. The Health Insurance Act guarantees access to freedom of access to

medical care to the insured, and the patient's right to chose should not be geographically or administratively limited.

Patients constantly complain about the insufficient number of referrals. In this regard we conducted a questionnaire-based survey among patients to find their attitudes to paid physical exams by specialist physicians.

ANALYSIS

The goal of this research is to assess and analyse the respondents' attitudes to paid specialist physical exams in outpatient care.

The study is a part of a larger questionnaire-based research related to specialised outpatient care. It was conducted in the 18.04.2023 - 31.07.2023 period through the Google Forms online platform. 509 patients from all over the country responded. 63.3% of them were women and 36.7% were men. The largest proportion of respondents fell in the 31-40 age range - 31.6%, followed by the 41-50 age group - 24.2%, and the over 60 age group -22.6%. The age under 30 age group was had the smallest number - 7.3%.

The questions regarding the respondents' social status shows that more than 3/4 (76%) of them are employed, followed by the those who are unemployed - 9.8%, the students (5.8%) and the retirees - 5.7 %.

It was established that the majority of the respondents' income fits in two ranges - that between 1001 and 1500BGN and that between 1501 and 2000BGN - with 25.3 % for both groups. They are followed by the 2001-3400BGN ranges - 15.7 %, with the 801-1000BGN range in third place - 14,3 %. It is concerning that 10.8% of the participants reported an income under 800BGN. The size of the monthly income affects people's ability to satisfy their needs, which has an effect on the quality of life. Low-income patients cannot afford health services not included in the NHIF's package, paid services, costly treatment. This has an indirect impact on the quality of health services they are provided with.

When asked "Would you go to a paid physical exam with a specialist, under the condition that only 90% of the price is immediately reimbursed?", 66.4 % of the participants give an affirmative answer. According to 12.4 % of the respondents, the entirety of the sum

paid should be reimbursed, while 11.4 % would not agree to go through an exam under those conditions. A not insignificant part - 9,8 % were unable to give an answer.

Figure 1. Would you go to a paid physical exam with a specialist, under the condition that only 90% of the price is immediately reimbursed?

In order to clarify the respondents' attitude to fully paid specialist physical exams, we asked the question "How would you describe your attitude to fully paid physical exams with a specialist?" (Figure 2). The results show that the negative answers are the majority -

23% of the participants do not approve of paid exams with a specialist at all, and those who mostly disapprove are 38.3%. Only 13.6% fully approve of paid physical exams by a specialist, while 1/4 (25.1 %) approve of them mostly.

Figure 2. Patient attitudes to fully paid physical exams by a specialist

The respondents were asked what they thought the cost of seeing a specialist should be (Figure 3). According to 38.9% of the respondents, the price for a specialist exam should be between 20 and 50 BGN, while 27.7% believe that the price should be between 50 and 70 BGN, and 11.8% - between 90 and 110 BGN. Only

4.9% responded that the price should be determined by the specialist's qualifications. The responses to this question showcase the patients' ignorance of the real cost of medical services. Most likely, this is a consequence of the current health care system and the poor information campaigns in this area.

Figure 3. The participants' opinions on the he cost of seeing a specialist

The respondents were asked whether they thought there were advantages to a paid physical exam with a specialist over one carried out with a GP referral (Figure 4). According to 60.9% of the respondents, a paid

exam by a specialist has advantages over one performed with a referral from a GP, while nearly ¼ (24.2%) believe that there is no such advantage. 14.9% could not determine whether there was an advantage to seeing a paid specialist.

Figure 4. Respondents' opinion on the presence of advantages to a paid physical exam with a specialist over one carried out with a GP referral

The respondents who gave affirmative answers were asked to indicate what they considered to be the advantages of a paid physical exam by a specialist over one carried out with a referral from a GP (Table 1). The first reason given by respondents was that paid physical

exams are carried out with better tools and in better conditions (39.7 %), followed by that they are conducted more promptly (39.5 %). According to 14.9%, paid exams are carried out by more qualified specialists, while 13.9% stated that they are more accessible.

The total exceeds 100% as there was the opportunity to give multiple answers.

Table 1.

Advantages to a paid physical exams with a specialist over one carried out with a GP referral, according to the participants

Advantages	number	%
A paid exam is carried out by more qualified specialist	76	14.9%
A paid exam is conducted more promptly	201	39.5%
A paid exam is carried out with better tools and in better conditions	202	39.7%
A paid exam is more accessible	71	13.9%
Other	11	2.2%

When asked "In which cases would you be willing to fully cover the cost of a physical exam with a specialist?", 68,4 % indicated they would do it in case of emergency or urgency. Over half the participates - 51,1 %, indicated they would in case they need to get a second

opinion on a pre-existing diagnosis. About 1/3 (32.4%) would prefer to visit a particular specialist recommended to them who does not work with referrals, and only 3.3% could not answer.

Table 2.

Respondents' opinion on cases in which they willing to fully cover the cost of a physical exam

responses	number	%
In case of emergency or urgency	348	68.4%
To get a second opinion on a pre-existing diagnosis	260	51.1%
To visit a particular specialist recommended to me who does not work with referrals	165	32.4%
I cannot determine	17	3.3%

CONCLUSION

The following conclusions can be drawn from the analysis of the results presented:

1. 61.3% of the participants do not fully approve of paid specialist physical exams.
2. According to 60.9% of the respondents, a paid exam by a specialist has advantages over one performed with a referral from a GP, while nearly ¼ (24.2%) believe that there is no such advantage.
3. The main advantages of paid exams that the respondents point to are that those exams are carried out with better tools and in better conditions (39.7 %) and that they are conducted more promptly (39.5 %).
4. Only 14.9% believe that paid exams are carried out by more qualified specialists.
5. 68.4 % of the participants are willing to fully cover the cost of a physical exam with a specialist in case of emergency or urgency, while 51.1 % in case they need to get a second opinion for an existing diagnosis.

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